

HUMAN CAPITAL AS AN INTEGRAL PART OF NATIONAL WEALTH

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It is known that every national state has its own national wealth. National wealth is the sum of investment created by society and expressed in monetary units. National wealth consists of: a) natural resources, b) material resources, c) spiritual resources. An integral part of national wealth is national capital. National capital is also the sum of national production capital, national natural capital, national human capital and national financial capital. National human capital includes social and political capital, priority national intellectual directions, national competitiveness and natural potential of the nation.

Today, the gross national human capital of the countries of the world is 550 trillion dollars, and half of this amount belongs to the leading capitalist countries such as France, Germany, Italy, Canada, Japan, the United States, and Great Britain. In particular, it is estimated that the national capital of America is 24 trillion dollars, and the gross national wealth of the CIS countries is around 80 trillion dollars. National human capital is about half of the national wealth of developing countries, while in developed countries this indicator is about 70-80%. Because, at present, human capital is a separate, intensive and complex factor of socio-economic development, and it appears as a guarantee of economic growth based on innovations and high technologies. Its difference from natural resources, classic labor and usual types of capital is that it always requires a high level of investment in itself, it wants a certain period of time for the profit from these investments. In the 1990s, in developed countries, 70 percent of all investments were spent on human capital, and about 30 percent of investments were spent on fixed capital. The state takes over the majority of investments in human capital, which is one of the main levers of the state's direction of the economy. However, national human capital remains the main factor of intensive development of the economy today.

The main signs and characteristics of the formation and implementation of human capital are as follows:

- Human capital requires a certain amount of expenditure from the person himself and society (state);
- Human capital is a reserve that is constantly replenished and improved as knowledge, skills and experience;
- Human capital can also wear out, lose its value and require additional cost;

- Investments spent on human capital provide its owner with high income and profit;
- Investments in human capital will have large-scale and long-lasting economic and social benefits;
- The investment period of human capital is much longer than that of material capital. For example, for fixed capital, this period is 1-5 years, for human capital in the form of educational capital, this period is 1220 years;
- Human capital differs from material capital in terms of liquidity. It is directly related to its owner - a living person.
- Regardless of who owns the financial resources used for its formation (family, state or sponsors), the use of human capital and the benefits it brings is decided by a specific person;
- The existence of human capital and its use are closely related to the subject's free will, his will, his material and moral interest, outlook, responsibility, general cultural level.

Human capital is not only an economic category and concept, the current interpretations of human capital came to the fore because this issue first came to the attention of economists and it is directly related to the economic situation and development of a particular country.

Formation of human capital

Education Health care

Increase in labor productivity

Development of science and technology

Economic growth

The topic of human capital is a subject of investigation not only for economists, but also for philosophers, sociologists, pedagogues and psychologists. For example, philosophers study the system of spiritual qualities formed in a person in the process of gathering life experience, education, and work, while sociologists study the relationship of these experiences and skills, knowledge and imagination with society and the social environment in which it lives, and the science of pedagogy as a means of education and training. It is necessary to carry out research on the knowledge, experience and skills formed in a person, and psychology should shed light on the problem of the impact of the knowledge, experience and skills formed on a person on cognitive (relationship with human mentality and potential) and human behavior.

World civilizations and their relationship with forms of human capital. It should be recognized that the development of national forms of human capital in the

world was determined by the historical development path of world civilizations and countries. In particular, the investments in education and science in Western European and North American countries in the 19th century, as well as during the transition to industrial and post-industrial society, led to the rapid development of Western civilization and their complete superiority in all areas of other civilizations and countries, such as China, India, Islamic countries, and Russia. , paved the way for the Anglo-Saxon race to become the dominant civilization in the world. This shows that even in the Middle Ages, investments in people (although the concept of human capital was not put into circulation) ultimately became the basis for the development of one or another civilization, and caused the crisis of those who did not start this work.

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